

An Integrated Environment for Medical Training and Procedure Planning in Virtual Reality

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Abstract—The scientific community is increasingly considering the adoption of virtual environments in medicine. In particular, surgical planning, navigation, and training can be highly effective when coupling digital twins of the human body with haptic devices. In this preliminary work, the aim is to interact with objects -specifically a 3D model of a section of the abdomen- in Virtual Reality, getting the tactile perception of internal organ palpation through a wearable haptic interface. The developed environment enables the integration of additional devices and services, thus allowing its use for both medical training and medical procedure planning.

Index Terms—Simulation, virtual reality, haptics, grasping.

I. INTRODUCTION

Frenetic technological advancement involves every field, and medicine is no exception. Indeed part of the development revolves around simulations for surgical planning and, more in general, medical training in a virtual -and controlled- environment, complete with 3D models of the human body. Within these environments surgeons can plan and rehearse surgeries without endangering the patient; to aid physicians in comprehending intricate anatomical structures, anticipating potential problems, and providing a more authentic experience, the use of Virtual Reality (VR) and Haptic Devices is becoming increasingly promising. The work presented develops in this context: the aim is to *touch* a CT-reconstructed section of an abdomen with a digital hand - detailed in II-A- in 3D VR visually rendered through an Oculus Rift S [1] and dynamically simulated in the CoppeliaSIM robotic simulation environment [2]. Human users receive haptic feedback on the hand wearing the Weart TouchDIVER (TD) haptic interface [3], which also controls the digital hand. The interaction tasks considered in this preliminary work are:

- 1) Palpation, namely grasping organs of the digital abdomen model with the capability of moving them, receiving force feedback through the thimbles of the TD.
- 2) Texture feeling, meaning that objects with varying textures produce distinct frequencies of vibrations.
- 3) Temperature feeling, i.e., organs or lesions may exhibit slight temperature variations that can be reproduced.

The original contribution of this work, enabling the achievement of the above-mentioned tasks, is:

- The combination of CoppeliaSIM, TD, and Oculus within an integrated simulation framework.
- The development of a 5-finger hand model.

- Real to virtual hand motion retargeting based on the information provided by the TD.

II. ENVIRONMENT

The aforementioned interactions occur within a scene of CoppeliaSIM with a (right) robotic hand (shown in Fig. 1),

and both a digital phantom of a section of the abdomen and, for illustrative purpose, two basic shapes lying atop a table. The virtual robotic hand reproduces the movements of the user's gloved one. In particular, the articulation of the fingers is determined through the information provided by the TD¹, and the position of the hand through the tracking functionality offered by the controller of the VR device, i.e., the position of the robotic hand is consistent with that of the VR device controller placed on the user's wrist (see Fig. 2). The employment of the VR device is made possible by the additional functionality provided by CoppeliaSIM, i.e., a specific plugin that enabled the integration of this device. The CoppeliaSIM VR Interface plugin allows an immersion into the 3D virtual scene. Thus, it is independent of the developed architecture that realizes the proper communication between devices with the simulator.

¹Considering that the haptic device used has only three thimbles for the thumb, index, and middle fingers, the ring and little finger of the virtual hand close and open together with the middle one, commanded by the user.

Fig. 1. Hand model with semi-cardioid paths for each fingertip.

A. Robotic hand

A virtual robotic hand has been developed that reflects the anthropometry of a real hand. Position-controlled rotational joints are placed between each of the three links of the five fingers of a robotic hand 3D model; joint limits are specified to avoid non-physiological movements.

1) *Path design for motion retargeting*: For retargeting the motion of the human's hand to the virtual one a path is assigned to each fingertip since, for similar tasks, the paths are unlikely to vary significantly, whereas tracking every conceivable finger movement would be needlessly complicated. [4], [5]. The curve chosen to approximate the fingertips trajectories in grasping is half of a reversed cardioid function, obtained by parametrizing the cardioid consistently with the information provided by the TD. In particular, for each fingertip, the TD provides a normalized value, the *time-of-flight*, that is proportional to the distance of the fingertips to the sensor positioned on the user's wrist. Therefore, this value provides information about the current hand configuration with respect to the closed one. The 2D path of each fingertip is parameterized as follows:

$$\begin{cases} x = \sin(s)(1 - \cos(s)) \\ y = -(1 - \cos(s))\cos(s) \end{cases} \quad s = \text{TimeOfFlight}. \quad (1)$$

The path is then attributed to each fingertip and adapted to the length of the finger and its position relative to the center of the palm. To employ the inverse kinematic function of CoppeliaSIM, five dummy targets -one for each finger- must follow the predetermined paths as shown in Fig 1.

2) *Grasping*: Grasping is simulated as a magnetic attachment. CoppeliaSim allows its simulation using a force sensor called *attachPoint* to be combined with a proximity sensor. Both are in the center of the robotic hand palm. If fingers are closed beyond a predefined *closure* value, and the proximity sensor detects the closeness to an object, the latter sticks to the *attachPoint* as a magnet. Despite its simplicity, this solution provides the feeling of a realistic grip.

For demonstration, in the accompanying video, the grasped objects are a cube and the right kidney inside the phantom. Unlike the cube, placed directly on the table, the kidney is *floating* within an empty concavity (the abdominal section), so gravity causes it to fall. Therefore, force control is implemented to ensure that: if no grasping force is detected, the kidney remains in its original position; otherwise, the latter changes to match that of the robotic hand.

The implemented grasplings are: grabbing an object with all fingers, between the thumb and index finger, or between the thumb, the middle, the ring, and the little finger (Fig. 2).

III. FEEDBACK

While the grasping task requires information to be sent from the haptic device, and acquired as specific poses in the virtual scene, feedback information flows backward. In CoppeliaSIM, upon hand contact with the objects touched, the function *getContactInfo* returns: the identifier of the contact elements,

Fig. 2. Grasping the cube with all the fingers. Note that the finger clasp adapts to the shape of the object taken

the normal vector of contact points, and a force vector. Based on this information, it is determined whether the interaction results in feedback and what type it is. The TD can render three different characteristics of the sense of touch: force, temperature, and texture. The implemented examples render the interactions as follows.

- Force feedback (FF). TD returns FF as the pressure exerted by moving platforms inside the thimbles and felt when the virtual hand grasps the cube or the kidney.
- Temperature and texture feedback. By stroking the fat enveloping the abdominal section, the TD returns a combination of vibrations reminiscent of the leather texture and a fictitious warm temperature. The table also renders feedback, specifically an oak wood texture and a cold temperature².

IV. SOFTWARE ARCHITECTURE

The developed system extends the framework illustrated in Fig. 3, originally presented in [6], refined in [7] and currently available on GitHub.

The framework simplifies development by providing a logical architecture that allows modular adaptations and sectoral expansions and fosters collaborative development. A standard framework structure includes a Proxy Layer (PL), Business Logic Layer (BLL), Entity Layer (EL), and Database Layer (DL). The description in hierarchical order of the aforementioned layers follows.

- 1) PL includes all the classes that interface with the physical devices connected to the framework. The current work incorporates the *WeartProxy* class within the PL which deals with running the haptic device thread, allowing it to get and set values of its interest in runtime. At the PL, a VR class is not a requirement to realize communication with the Oculus device since

²The table and the fat were chosen as large enough to make the two feedbacks appreciable.

the CoppeliaSIM VR Interface plugin was exploited as mentioned earlier.

- 2) BLL is responsible for the description and implementation of high-level tasks. Specific to our work at that level *Force Feedback Palpation Strategy* (FFPS) and *Control Context* classes are within. In the former, the signals produced in CoppeliaSIM by the interaction of the virtual hand with the objects are captured, and it also takes real-time positions of the three fingertips from the haptic device. Whereas, the *Control Context* class handles the defined tasks with all the devices. The changes in this class contribute to achieving the goal task by catching the signals sent from the FFPS class.
- 3) At the EL, each class represents an atomic component called up in the calculations of higher-level tasks. Each object exists as an abstract element that serves the higher task classes to be able to process data. There is no difference between the physical and simulated devices at this layer.
- 4) DL interfaces with all configuration files to read and write data during task execution.

The two highest layers are the only ones modified in the present work: the PL - improving the interaction and exploiting the full potential of the haptic device - and the BLL implementing the goal task, i.e., FFPS.

A. Information flow

In this work, information flows in two opposite directions: in one way, for the transmission of feedback from CoppeliaSIM to the haptic device, and in the other opposite direction, for the transmission of the physical hand's closure value.

Fig. 3. The Framework developed in [6], and [7] with the integration proposed in this work.

Once triggered by a virtual interaction, the transmission of feedback begins by taking in PL force signals and the identifiers of the objects touched, and via the FFPS class, and subsequently the Entity layer, transmitted to the Control Context class. The latter allows the Weart Proxy class to render force, temperature and texture feedback.

Conversely, the transmission of the closure value, identified by the TD, must travel up the flow to reach the virtual scene. This is initially done via the WeartProxy class, which takes the closure value from the haptic device, allowing the FFPS class to detect it and update the graphic render in CoppeliaSIM.

V. CONCLUSION

This work presents an innovative combination of CoppeliaSIM, TD and VR allowing retargeting of the motion of the hand of a user wearing the TD to a custom-developed 5-finger 3R robotic hand, actuated through position-controlled joints.

The robotic hand consistently interacts with the scene objects. Indeed, the graphics engine of the simulation environment effectively renders simple shapes. This is not the case for complex and multifaceted objects, such as those belonging to a 3D model of a CT-reconstructed section of an abdomen, especially in VR. Therefore, due to rendering constraints, only the left kidney -which has a rather simple form- is made dynamic and graspable in the demonstration.

Future work includes improving simulation performance and the integration of deformable objects.

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